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Review Article

A Review On Extensive Assessment Of The Oral Formulations Enriched With Chamomile For Optimal Oral Care

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ABSTRACT

It is a about the exhaustive analysis of review explores the extensive assessment of orals formulation enriched with chamomile for optimal oral care. The chamomile plant is multifaceted and acceptable herb which have the rich historical background in medical applications like therapeutic properties or action on anti-inflammatory, antioxidants and analgesic effects. The review begins with the introduction to chamomile oral formulation and significance of chamomile plant. Chamomile plant extract have different types of administration based on formulation of drug. In that oral pathway continues to stand out as one of the prevalent and friendly approach for administering drugs likes tablet, capsules and mouthwash etc. The therapeutic action of the drug as anti-inflammatory, antioxidants, analgesic effect are providing the comprehensive understanding of the oral care. The articles explain about the various different applications of chamomile drug like smoothing the skin or improve skin health , control the irritation of skin , relived stress , improve sleep and other problems. These are the application benefits which are by using chamomile drugs like Capsule, herbal tea, tablet and mouthwash. In addition to its therapeutic effects the review address about the safety profile of chamomile when the drug administered and minimum drug toxicity.

conclusion:

The review provides information regarding the chamomile oral formulations. By emphasizing the chamomile's pharmacological activities, applications, and market availability, it ensuring the possibility of chamomile as a natural and effective ingredient in oral health care formulations.

INTRODUCTION

The oral formulations are defined as the developing and manufacturing of medications

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intended for oral administration. The drug administered to the body through the oral route are absorbed in the gastrointestinal track, intestine, stomach. The tablets and capsules are the popular examples for the oral drug delivery system. The oral route administration has the many advantages compare to the other route of administration of drug. Now a days the oral formulations are developed lot for the pediatrics.[1] The chamomile shows the variety of therapeutic activity while administering through orally. The chamomile can administer orally it is not showing any toxic effect to body.[2] With its roles as an anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and mild astringent, chamomile has many health benefits. Chamomile's aroma has been shown to have calming effects, using it in aromatherapy may help lessen anxiety and insomnia.[3] In ancient Egypt, chamomile was revered for its healing properties and was associated with the gods of the sun.[4] It was commonly used to treat malaria. Throughout history, chamomile has been utilized for various purposes, including aiding digestion, freshening breath, boosting immunity, promoting restful sleep and meditation, serving as a general tonic, alleviating allergies, addressing women's menstrual problems, treating bronchitis, combating worms and insect bites, and relieving itching.[5] The chamomile shows the beneficial action on the oral formulations. The review explores the chemical constituents, application, anti-inflammatory activity, antimicrobial activity and analgesic activity of chamomile plant and the oral formulations on chamomile available on market for optimal oral care.

DETAILED DISCRIPTION OF CHAMOMILA:

Plants have long been known to have health benefits for humans. Herbs have been used extensively in conventional and alternative

medicine for at least 5000 years. The long-lasting appeal of herbal remedies can be ascribed to their effects' gradual furthermore usually non-toxic nature. Dried flowers of the *Matricaria* species are used to make chamomile it is one of the most broadly used herbs for medicinal therapeutic purposes. It is obtained in the forms of standardized tea and herbal extracts. One of the most predominantly used, researched, traditional therapeutic plants in the world, chamomile has been considered for a various number of medical uses.[6] The term Chamomile originates from the Greek language, signifying "ground apple". This is probably because of its delightful apple-like aroma, which is linked to its use in spells for prosperity, harmony, love, peace, and purification.[5] German chamomile, wild chamomile (*Matricaria discoidea* DC.), German chamomile, *Matricaria Aurea* Loeffl., *Matricaria occidentalis* G., field or corn chamomile (*Anthemis arvensis* L.), stinking chamomile (*Anthemis cotula* L.), scentless or false chamomile (*Trileurospermum inodorum* L.), dyer's chamomile (*Cota tinctoria* L.), and other botanical species are recognized as chamomile. In order to prevent confusion, the botanical name for chamomile that belongs to the *Chamomilla* L. genus is currently recognized as *Matricaria recutita* L. (also known as *Matricaria chamomilla* or *Chamomilla recutita*). A distinct feature that sets true chamomile apart from other types is the unpleasant smell that either precedes or follows the otherwise pleasant scent. German chamomile (*M. chamomilla* L.) and Roman or English chamomile (*Chamaemelum nobile* syn. *Anthemis nobilis* L.) are the two primary species of chamomile that are commonly used for medicinal purposes. Furthermore, a third type species that is commonly utilized in the fragrance together with cosmetics fields is called Moroccan chamomile, or

Ormenis multicaulis Braun-Blanq. & Maire. When it comes to biological effects, *M. chamomilla* L. outperforms other species. It is established as "alleszutraut" in German, which indicated as "it can do anything," and is considered a panacea in Europe. Chamomile is often drunk as a tea or tonic and is generally safe for constipation. Flavonoids, volatile oils, coumarins, sterols, organic acids, terpenes, and polysaccharides are some of the constituents that make up chamomile.[4] Dried chamomile is frequently taken as a tea or tonic and is generally thought to be safe to consume. It is an essential component of many homeopathic, traditional, and Unani medicinal formulations. Its primary uses are for treating mild skin irritation and for managing ailments like inflammation, depression, anxiety,[7] sedation, and spasms.[8] Numerous pharmacological effects are exhibited by chamomile, such as its potential as an antidepressant, anticarcinogenic activity,[9] hypoglycemic, hypotension, antiallergic,[10] hypolipidemic, anti-Alzheimer's,[11] anti-infective, anti-asthmatic,[12] anti-cancer,[13] treatment of insulin resistance polycystic ovary syndrome,[14] anti-inflammatory,[15] treat obesity,[10] treating premenstrual syndrome,[17] angiogenesis activity,[7] antibacterial,[18] and antioxidant.[4] *M. chamomilla* is used to treat an extensive range of conditions, such as improving digestion, improving breath, boosting immunity, encouraging peaceful sleep and meditation, acting as a general tonic, easing allergies, helping women with menstrual problems, curing bronchitis, fighting worms and insect bites, and relieving itching.[5] A popular herbal tea, chamomile is made from the dried flowers of *Matricaria recutita* L. This plant produces white flowers with a yellow-orange center that are aromatic, flavorful, and have coloring qualities. A wide range of commercial products, including herbal teas,

alcoholic beverages, confections baked goods, hair products, ointments, lotions, perfumes, detergents, soap, use infusions with essential oils that are extracted from the fresh or dried flower heads. Interestingly, chamomile flowers consist a volatile oil with a blue color and a concentration that varies from 0.24 to 2.0 percent. A minimal of 4 mL/kg of blue essential oil is required in chamomile, according to the European Pharmacopoeia.[4] Overall, this plant offers exceptional research potential. Nevertheless, the literature has very few reviews of it.

Classification of *M. chamomilla*:

Division	↔	Magnoliophyta
Super division	↔	Spermatophyta
Kingdom	↔	Plantae-Plants
Class	↔	Magnoliopsida
Subclass	↔	Asteridae
Family	↔	Asteraceae
Order	↔	Asterales

Chamomile Plant Parts

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS:

After much research, scientists have been discovered more than 120 constituents in chamomile flowers. Terpenoids, which account for 78% on the essential oil extracted from chamomile flowers, include alfa-bisabolol and its oxides. Furthermore, the oil contains chamazulene, a kind of azuline, in concentrations ranging from 1 to 15%.[19] Proazulenes and chamazulene carboxylic acid are additionally found in chamomile. From the essential oils of the chamomile species *Matricaria recutita*, precocenes have been isolated. German chamomile essential oil has been found to specifically inhibit the production of aflatoxin G (1), and active compounds like (E)- and (Z)-Spiro ethers have been isolated from the oil. Other substances found in the volatile oil include spathulenol, cis/trans-en-in-dicycloether (8–20%), and farnesene (12–28%). There are 11 bioactive phenolic compounds found in chamomile extract: phenylpropanoids (such as chlorogenic acid and caffeic acid), coumarins (such as herniarin and umbelliferon) flavones (such as luteolin, luteolin-7-O-glucoside, and apigenin), flavanols (such as rutin and quercetin), and flavanone (naringenin).[19] Also,

phenolic substances such as luteolin, patuletin, apigenin, quercetin, and their glucosides are present in chamomile flowers.[20] Azulenes such as chamazulene and terpenoids such as alfa-bisabolol and its oxides are the main component of essential oil extracted from the chamomile flower.[21] The chamomile flower extracted essential oil has more numerous substance that contains the significant medicinal value.[22] Also, mucilage, coumarins, flavonoids, and mono- and oligosaccharides all show pharmacological effects. It is possible to separate these compounds from the plant's aqueous extract through fractionation.[23]

APPLICATIONS OF CHAMOMILE:

1. Chamomile tea is renowned for its soothing effects and can aid in promoting relaxation and improving sleep quality.[5]
2. Chamomile is a great natural hair rinse for people who want to add a gorgeous golden glow to their blonde or light-colored hair.[5]
3. The pleasant scent of chamomile has the ability to reduce stress, which makes it a great option for easing anxiety. By adding a few drops of chamomile essential oil to a diffuser or taking a soothing bath with chamomile water, you can take advantage of its benefits.[5]
4. Applying chamomile topically helps relieve skin irritations such as sunburns, rashes, and eczema.[5]
5. Chamomile tea can help ease indigestion or upset stomach symptoms by calming the digestive tract and minimizing bloating.[5]
6. To alleviate tired and puffy eyes, simply utilize chamomile tea bags as a compress for a soothing effect.[5]
7. For optimal oral health, consider incorporating chamomile mouthwash or

gargling with chamomile tea to soothe gum inflammation and alleviate mouth sores.[5]

8. Chamomile tea can help women who are suffering from PMS symptoms or menstrual cramps by easing discomfort and lessening the intensity of symptoms.[5]

9. The anti-inflammatory qualities of chamomile tea can help reduce the symptoms of allergies, such as itchy eyes and sneezing.[5]

10. When seeking a natural insect repellent, chamomile essential oil can effectively keep mosquitoes and other bugs at bay.[5]

Anti-inflammatory Activity of Chamomile:

Volatile oils found in chamomile flowers include α -bisabolol, α -bisabolol oxides A and B, and matricin, which is typically transformed into chamazulene. They also contain additional flavonoids with anti-inflammatory and antiphlogistic qualities.[24] The flavonoids and essential oils found in chamomile can reach the skin's deeper layers, according to research done on human volunteers. Their effectiveness as topical anti-inflammatory agents depend on these characteristics. One way chamomile reduces inflammation is by preventing prostaglandin E2 from being released in response to lipopolysaccharide (LPS) and by reducing the activity of the enzyme cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), while leaving COX-1 in its constitutive form unaffected.[16]

Antimicrobial Activity of Chamomile:

The anti-microbial properties of chamomile volatile oil have been shown in its capacity to prevent the growth of bacteria and fungus. It can also be applied to treat urticaria and effectively

lowers the levels of protease in mites. The chamomile plant naturally produces a peptide called MCh-AMP1, which has broad-spectrum antifungal activity against yeasts and molds that are harmful to humans. By increasing the permeability of cell membranes and triggering the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), it eradicates *Candida albicans* efficiently. According to a study by Shikov et al., chamomile extract's minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC90) and minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC50) against *Helicobacter pylori* were 125 and 62.5 mg/mL, respectively. Moreover, by altering the shape and fermentation potential of *H. pylori*, this extract controls the urease production. Many chamomile-containing mouthwashes and sprays are currently used in clinical products for oral bacteriostasis, such as the White Gold Medal *Compositae* essence Product.[4]

Analgesic Activity of Chamomile:

Centuries ago, Chamomile was already being utilized as a remedy for alleviating various types of pain, including arthralgia, stomach cramps, and

neuralgia. Modern research has demonstrated the analgesic benefits of chamomile oil gel, particularly in the treatment of aura-free migraine pain. Saghafi et al. also carried out a study that proved chamomile's efficacy in treating breast discomfort. Patients in the study received chamomile treatment for eight weeks, and the degree of pain relief was measured with a breast pain scale (BPC) and a visual analogue scale (VAS).[4]

Wound healing:

The chamomile aqueous extract (120 mg/kg/day) demonstrated a higher rate of wound contraction in addition to a higher hydroxyproline content and wound-breaking strength. In rats, chamomile extract applied as rubbing oil showed promise in hastening the healing of burn injuries. In a linear incisional wound model of rats, topically applied chamomile extract has the potential to promote wound healing. When compared to animals given corticosteroids, animals given chamomile showed noticeably quicker wound healing.[19]

ORAL FORMULATIONS:

The oral formulations are referred as the drugs which are developed and manufactured for oral administrations for show their therapeutic activity. The variety of oral formulations are developed in the pharmaceuticals such as tablets, capsules and syrups...etc. [26]

The oral formulations are,

- **Solids:**

MARKETLY AVAILABLE CHAMOMILE ORAL FORMULATIONS

Tablets, Capsules, Pellets, Powders, Granules, herbal tea, Premixes and Thin strips.

- **Semisolids:**

Pastes, and Gels.

- **Liquids:**

Solutions, Syrups, Emulsions, Suspensions, Elixirs and mouthwashes.[1]

Chamomile Extract

Chamomile Capsule

Chamomile Mouthwash

Chamomile Mouth Spray

Chamomile Elixir

Chamomile Capsules

Chamomile Tea

Chamomile Pellets

Blue Chamomile Hydrosol

Chamomile Elixir

Chamomile oil

Chamomile Flower powder

Chamomile contain Toothpaste

Ginger Chamomile anti-emetic Tablet

GINGER&CHAMOMILE TABLETS: A Tablet is a compressed unit of solid dosage form that contain medicaments with or without excipients.

COMPOSITION:

Ginger and Chamomile extract.....7gm/tablet.....API

Moringa powder.....2gm/tablet.....

Binder
Lactose

MCC.....19.5gm/tablet...Di
luents

Magnesium
stearate.....1.2gm/tablet.....Lubri
cant

In addition to the ginger and chamomile extract, lactose MCC, magnesium stearate, and moringa powder were utilized as a binder, diluent, and lubricant. Then the tablet was made using the wet granulation technique.[27]

APPLICATION:

- The anti-emetic properties of ginger and chamomile tablets make them useful for treating nausea and vomiting.

- For seasonal cold and flu, chamomile and ginger make an ideal combination.
- It can be used to treat morning sickness in the first trimester of pregnancy.
- In the short term, taking it orally for medical purposes may be safe.
- It improves digestion.
- It has soothing effects on the stomach.[27]

CHAMOMILE PELLETS:

Pellets are the small free flowing spherical particulates prepared by the appropriate methods. The pellets having the several advantages in preparation process compare to the tablets and capsules because of its multi-particulate delivery system. Pellets having several advantages while administered through the oral route, including decreased food effect, lower gastric transit time, less gastrointestinal tract irritation, and decreased intra- and inter-subject variability. Considering the various advantages of pellets, M. chamomilla pellets are prepared by extrusion-spheronization technique.[28] Chemicals which are used to prepare the chamomile pellets are, Polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), Avicel PH101, sodium starch glycolate (SSG), maize starch, lactose, sodium

carbonate, sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS), aluminum chloride, Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, magnesium stearate (MS), isopropanol and ethanol.[28]

CHAMOMILE CAPSULES:

Chamomile is used in the polycystic syndrome treatment as an herbal remedy, according to traditional herbal medicine. Patients' total testosterone levels significantly decreased after taking chamomile capsules orally. And the capsules are prepared as a dietary supplement and anxiety treatment.[29]

CHAMOMILE TEAS:

Herbal teas are the most liked liquid refreshment throughout the world, the herbal tea shows as both therapeutic and also nutritional benefit in many traditional medical forms.[30] Herbal teas are more appropriately called "tisanes," as they are blends of various ingredients. The dried leaves, seeds, grasses, nuts, barks, fruits, flowers, or other botanical components that give herbal teas their flavor and health benefits are combined to create tisanes.[31] The chamomile is ideal for use as a sleep aid due to its gentle sedative effect. Additionally, it functions as a mild laxative and relieves stomach discomfort. It also helps to treat menstrual cramps.[31]

CHAMOMILE EXTRACT:

The Chamomile extraction process conducted by various methods.[27]

E.g.; THE EXTRACTION OF CHAMOMILE IN SOXHLET APPARATUS:

- Take 35 grams of powdered chamomile. The flask containing the chamomile powder was then filled with 100 ml of absolute ethanol solvent.
- The procedure involved six heat cycles in a heating mantle for one hour, all done at 78.40 C for a total of twelve hours.

The extract used to formulate various formulation in the pharmaceutical industry.[27]

CHAMOMILE SYRUP:

Using the chamomile syrup for Childrens having leukemia as a complementary therapy, that boost their immunity (since it increased WBC) by reducing the amount of neutropenia brought on by chemotherapy.[32]

CHAMOMILE-LEMON BALM SYRUP:

The herbal formulation of chamomile-lemon balm is significantly increasing the quality of life, anxiety, and depression, as well as angina symptoms in patients having drug-resistance cardiac syndrome x(CSX).[33]

CHAMOMILE MOUTHWASH:

The M. chamomilla flowerhead has been taken and air dried to prepare a powder, were the powder percolated successfully with 55% ethanol at room temperature. Then the ethanol extract is evaporated followed by filtration. The evaporation takes place under vacuum at lower temperature. Then the dried residue sustained in water. Thus, the extract is used as a mouthwash. The German chamomile mouthwash prepared for provide benefit in gingival and plaque reduction without any official adverse effect on tooth staining.[34]

For children with cancer, chamomile mouthwash and topical mouth rinse are effective short-term treatments to prevent oral mucositis. [35]

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the extensive assessment of oral formulations enriched with chamomile for optimal oral care underscores the herb's significant potential in promoting oral health. Chamomile's diverse therapeutic properties, including its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and analgesic effects, make it a valuable ingredient in oral health products such as tablets, capsules, and mouthwashes. Commercially available chamomile oral formulations offer promising avenues for addressing various oral health issues, while ongoing research and innovation continue to

uncover new insights into chamomile's benefits. Overall, chamomile emerges as a natural and effective option for enhancing oral hygiene and addressing oral health concerns, highlighting the importance of further exploration and utilization of this versatile herb in oral care practices.

REFERENCES

1. Strickley RG, Iwata Q, Wu S, Dahl TC. Pediatric drugs—a review of commercially available oral formulations. *Journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2008 May;97(5):1731-74. [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
2. Salehi B, Lopez-Jornet P, Pons-Fuster López E, Calina D, Sharifi-Rad M, Ramírez-Alarcón K, Forman K, Fernández M, Martorell M, Setzer WN, Martins N, Rodrigues CF, Sharifi-Rad J. Plant-Derived Bioactive in Oral Mucosal Lesions: A Key Emphasis to Curcumin, Lycopene, Chamomile, Aloe vera, Green Tea and Coffee Properties. *Biomolecules*. 2019 Mar 17;9(3):106. Doi: 10.3390/biom9030106. PMID: 30884918; PMCID: PMC6468600. [PUBMED]
3. Singh O, Khanam Z, Misra N, Srivastava MK. Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.): an overview. *Pharmacognosy reviews*. 2011 Jan;5(9):82. [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
4. Dai YL, Li Y, Wang Q, Niu FJ, Li KW, Wang YY, Wang J, Zhou CZ, Gao LN. Chamomile: a review of its traditional uses, chemical constituents, pharmacological activities and quality control studies. *Molecules*. 2022 Dec 23;28(1):133. [PUBMED]
5. Chauhan ES, Jaya A. Chamomile an ancient aromatic plant-A review. *J. Ayurveda Med. Sci*. 2017;2(4):251-5. [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
6. Janmejai K. Srivastava^{1,2,4}, Eswar Shankar^{1,2} and Sanjay Gupta¹⁻³ Department of Urology and Nutrition, 1Case Western Reserve University; 2University Hospitals Case Medical Center; 3Case Comprehensive Cancer Center, Cleveland, OH 44106, USA [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
7. Dolati S. A Review of the Therapeutic Effects of Chamomile (*Matricaria Chamomile*) in Traditional and Modern Medicine. *Researches in Sport Sciences and Medical Plants*. 2021 Feb 19;1(2):1-2. [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
8. Sah A, Naseef PP, Kuruniyan MS, Jain GK, Zakir F, Aggarwal G. A Comprehensive Study of Therapeutic Applications of Chamomile. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel)*. 2022 Oct 19;15(10):1284. Doi: 10.3390/ph15101284. PMID: 36297396; PMCID: PMC9611340. [PUBMED]
9. Miraj S, Alesaeidi S. A systematic review study of therapeutic effects of *Matricaria recuita chamomile* (chamomile). *Electronic physician*. 2016 Sep;8(9):3024. [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
10. Ali A, Tabanca N, Raman V, Avonto C, Yang X, DEMİRCİ B, Khan I, Chittiboyina A. Chemical Compositions of Essential Oils from German, Roman, and Chinese Chamomile Flowers and Their Biological Activities against Three Economically Important Insect Pests. *RECORDS OF NATURAL PRODUCTS*. 2023. [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
11. Alahmady NF, Alkhulaifi FM, Momenah MA, Alharbi AA, Allohibi A, Alsubhi NH, Alhazmi WA. Biochemical characterization of chamomile essential oil: Antioxidant, antibacterial, anticancer and neuroprotective activity and potential treatment for Alzheimer's disease. *Saudi Journal of*

- Biological Sciences. 2024 Feb 1;31(2):103912. [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
12. Li Q, Abdulla R, Xin X, Xue G, Kang X, Zhao F, Asia HA. Profiling of chemical constituents of *Matricaria chamomilla* L. by UHPLC-Q-Orbitrap-HRMS and in vivo evaluation its anti-asthmatic activity. *Heliyon*. 2023 May 1;9(5). [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 13. Maleki M, Mardani A, Manoochehri M, Ashghali Farahani M, Vaismoradi M, Glarcher M. Effect of chamomile on the complications of cancer: A systematic review. *Integrative Cancer Therapies*. 2023 Apr; 22:15347354231164600. [GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 14. Ashkar F, Rezaei S, Salahshornezhad S, Vahid F, Gholamalizadeh M, Dahka SM, Doaei S. The Role of medicinal herbs in treatment of insulin resistance in patients with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome: A literature review. *Biomol Concepts*. 2020 Mar 26;11(1):57-75. doi: 10.1515/bmc-2020-0005. PMID: 32229652. [PUBMED]
 15. Radovanović K, Gavarić N, Aćimović M. Anti-Inflammatory Properties of Plants from Serbian Traditional Medicine. *Life (Basel)*. 2023 Mar 24;13(4):874. doi: 10.3390/life13040874. PMID: 37109403; PMCID: PMC10146037. [PUBMED]
 16. Bayliak MM, Dmytriv TR, Melnychuk AV, Strilets NV, Storey KB, Lushchak VI. Chamomile as a potential remedy for obesity and metabolic syndrome. *EXCLI J*. 2021 Jul 26;20:1261-1286. doi: 10.17179/excli2021-4013. PMID: 34602925; PMCID: PMC8481792. [PUBMED]
 17. Khalesi ZB, Beiranvand SP, Bokaie M. Efficacy of chamomile in the treatment of premenstrual syndrome: a systematic review. *Journal of Pharmacopuncture*. 2019 Dec;22(4):[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 18. Mahdavi B, Ghorat F, Nasrollahzadeh MS, Hosseyni-Tabar M, Rezaei-Seresht H. Chemical composition, antioxidant, antibacterial, cytotoxicity, and hemolyses activity of essential oils from flower of *Matricaria chamomilla* var. *chamomilla*. *Anti-Infective Agents*. 2020 Sep 1;18(3):224-32.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 19. Gupta V, Mittal P, Bansal P, Khokra SL, Kaushik D. Pharmacological potential of *Matricaria recutita*-A review. *Int J Pharm Sci Drug Res*. 2010 Jan 1;2(1):12 6.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 20. Imad Hadi Hameed¹ , Ghaidaa Jihadi Mohammed² , Sabreen A. Kamal³ ¹ Biomedical Science Department, University of Babylon, College of Nursing, Hillah city, Iraq; ² Department of Biology, College of Science, University of Al-Qadisiyah, Hillah city, Iraq; ³ Department of Biology, College of Science for Women, University of Babylon, Hillah city, Iraq[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 21. Eddin LB, Jha NK, Goyal SN, Agrawal YO, Subramanya SB, Bastaki SMA, Ojha S. Health Benefits, Pharmacological Effects, Molecular Mechanisms, and Therapeutic Potential of α -Bisabolol. *Nutrients*. 2022 Mar 25;14(7):1370. doi: 10.3390/nu14071370. PMID: 35405982; PMCID: PMC9002489.[PUBMED]
 22. Catani MV, Rinaldi F, Tullio V, Gasperi V, Savini I. Comparative analysis of phenolic composition of six commercially available chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.) extracts: Potential biological implications. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*.

- 2021 Sep 30;22(19):10601.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
23. Sharifi-Rad M, Nazaruk J, Polito L, Morais-Braga MFB, Rocha JE, Coutinho HDM, Salehi B, Tabanelli G, Montanari C, Del Mar Contreras M, Yousaf Z, Setzer WN, Verma DR, Martorell M, Sureda A, Sharifi-Rad J. *Matricaria* genus as a source of antimicrobial agents: From farm to pharmacy and food applications. *Microbial Res.* 2018 Oct;215:76-88. doi: 10.1016/j.micres.2018.06.010. Epub 2018 Jun 25. PMID: 30172312.[PUBMED]
 24. El Mihyaoui A, Esteves da Silva JCG, Charfi S, Candela Castillo ME, Lamarti A, Arnao MB. Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.): A Review of Ethnomedicinal Use, Phytochemistry and Pharmacological Uses. *Life (Basel).* 2022 Mar 25;12(4):479. doi: 10.3390/life12040479. PMID: 35454969; PMCID: PMC9032859.[PUBMED]
 25. Akram W, Ahmed S, Rihan M, Arora S, Khalid M, Ahmad S, Ahmad F, Haque S, Vashishth R. An updated comprehensive review of the therapeutic properties of Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.). *International Journal of Food Properties.* 2024 Dec 31;27(1):133-64.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 26. Strickley RG. Pediatric oral formulations: an updated review of commercially available pediatric oral formulations since 2007. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2019 Apr 1;108(4):1335-65.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 27. Shah SA. To prepare and evaluate ginger: Chamomile anti-emetic tablet. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry.* 2023;12(5):236-44.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 28. Bolourchian N, Shirvani S, Mojab F. Development and evaluation of taste-masked pellets loaded with *Matricaria chamomilla* L. extract. *Journal of Medicinal Plants.* 2022 May 10;21(82):80-92.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 29. Heidary, Maryam; Yazdanpanahi, Zahra; Dabbaghmanesh, Mohammad Hossain¹; Parsanezhad, Mohammad Ebrahim²; Emamghoreishi, Masoumeh³; Akbarzadeh, Marzieh⁴, Effect of chamomile capsule on lipid- and hormonal-related parameters among women of reproductive age with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Journal of Research in Medical Sciences* 23(1):p 33, | DOI: 10.4103/jrms.JRMS_90_17.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 30. Poswal FS, Russell G, Mackonochie M, MacLennan E, Adukwu EC, Rolfe V. Herbal teas and their health benefits: a scoping review. *Plant Foods for Human Nutrition.* 2019 Sep 15;74:266-76.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 31. Ravikumar C. Review on herbal teas. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research.* 2014 May 1;6(5):236.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 32. Daneshfard B, Shahriari M, Heiran A, Nimrouzi M, Yarmohammadi H. Effect of chamomile on chemotherapy-induced neutropenia in pediatric leukemia patients: A randomized triple-blind placebo-controlled clinical trial. *Avicenna J Phytomed.* 2020 Jan-Feb;10(1):58-69. PMID: 31921608; PMCID: PMC6941685.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
 33. Noroozi S, Karimi M, Farahani AV, Omidi N, Zargaran A, Soleymani S, Alaeddini F, Rezaeizadeh H. Efficacy of Chamomile-Lemon Balm Syrup in Patients with Conventional Drug-Resistant Cardiac Syndrome X: A Single-Arm Clinical Trial. *Crescent Journal of Medical & Biological*

- Sciences. 2023 Apr 1;10(2).[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
34. Pourabbas R, Delazar A, Chitsazi MT. The effect of German chamomile mouthwash on dental plaque and gingival inflammation.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]
35. Motaghi M, Darbandi B, Baghersalimi A. Comparative effect of chamomile mouthwash and topical mouth rinse in prevention of chemotherapy-induced oral mucositis in Iranian pediatric patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia. *Iranian Journal of Blood and Cancer*. 2017 Sep 30;9(3):84-8.[GOOGLE SCHOLAR]

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